

Hemipteran predators: status, bio-ecology and rearing protocols

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Insects have a wide variety of predators, including birds, reptiles, amphibians, mammals, carnivorous plants, and other arthropods. Predators occur in most orders of insects but primarily in the beetle, dragon-fly, lacewing, wasp and true bug families like Coleoptera, Odonata, Neuroptera, Hemiptera and Diptera, respectively. Hemiptera are the largest of the non-Endo pterygote orders, with more than 90,000 species coming under 140 families. Hemipteran predators feeding on plants known for some time, this character unable them to live even in the prey scarcity period. They are the facultative zoophytophagous nature and the mouth parts are adopted both for plant and prey feeding. While some plant-feeding heteropterans are agricultural pests, others are valued biocontrol agents in agricultural ecosystems (Weirauch and schuh, 2011).

Hemipterans are broadly divided into two suborders as Homoptera and Heteroptera, of which heteropterans constitute most of the predatory bugs, where as their ancestors are phytophagous (Homopterans). Central to the evolution of these trophic shifts from phytophagy to predation has been evolutionarily claimed to the novel prey capturing strategies and envenomation (Weirauch and Schuh, 2011). These are widely distributed in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. They use an array of prey capturing strategies, such as Camouflage, venom injection, aggressive mimicry, sticky secretions, attract and imbibitions *etc* (Ferero *et al.*, 2011; Wignall and Taylor, 2010; Walker *et al.*, 2016).

The economically important hemipterans belong to Reduviidae, Pentatomidae, Anthocoridae, Miridae, Lygaeidae etc, which can be successfully used in agroecosystem for arthropod pest management. For the successful utilization of any bioagent, it is important to develop protocols for its mass production. Mass production protocols available for *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, *orius tancitillus*, *Eocanthecona furcellata*, *Rhynocoris marginatus*, *Geocoris ochropterus* etc are available (Liquidio, N. J and Nishida, T. 1985; Tripti and Chandish 2009; Lenin and Rajan 2016). The biology of *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* was studied on its natural prey. *Peregrinus maidis*. and a factitious prey, *Ceratitis capitata*. The body

dimensions of the predators fed on these two types of prey were equal. The duration of egg and nymphal instars were not significantly different however, the longevity of adults fed on natural prey was much longer than those fed on the factitious prey. The fecundity of *C. lividipennis* on *P. maidis* and *C. capitata* were identical. The predator had equal rates of increase when reared on the natural and fictitious prey. Therefore, *P. maidis* and *C. capitata* were equally suitable as prey of *C. lividipennis* (Liquido and Nishada 1986). *Eocanthecona furcellata* is an important predator for several agriculturally important pens The analyses showed that the total number of eggs of the predatory sink bug was 44 ± 8 days. incubation period 6 ± 1.05 days and the life cycle passed through five nymphal instars with a total nymphal period of about 16 ± 0.64 days. Male and female longevity were 12 ± 1.05 days and 14 ± 1.09 days, respectively, and total longevity period for male and female lasted 32 ± 0.19 and 36 ± 1.90 days, respectively. Moreover, this study revealed that *C. cephalomea* could be used as alternative host to mass rear *E. furcellata* when the main host is not available (Lenin and Rajan. 2016)

Besides their usefulness these bugs injurious to humans and other vertebrates by injecting venomous saliva. So, careful biosafety measures and improved rearing methodology for efficient mass rearing will be fruitful in the future. Since they are generalist predators and having pest control efficiency they can be used as effective tool in Bio- intensive integrated pest management.

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